

**AYURVEDIC APPROACH TO PSORIASIS MANAGEMENT: A HOLISTIC
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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18092391>**How to cite this Article:** *1Dr. Sanjeev Yadav, 2Dr. Prafulla, 3Dr. Sheetal Choudhari, 4Dr. Jitendra Pandagre. (2026) Ayurvedic Approach To Psoriasis Management: A Holistic Perspective. European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 13(1), 183-184. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

Article Received on 22/11/2025

Article Revised on 12/12/2025

Article Published on 01/01/2026

ABSTRACT

Psoriasis is an autoimmune disorder of skin results in hyper proliferation of the skin. It is a chronic skin disease characterized by dry skin and raised, rough, red areas on the skin covered with fine silvery scales. A clear skin description is available in Charaka Samhita under Kushtha. Ayurved management is quite effective in Psoriasis as compared to modern treatment. The line of treatment in present given study is Shodhan and Shaman Chikitsa. Virechan panchkarma therapy followed by internal medicinal treatment is considered as good management of skin disorder.

KEYWORDS: Psoriasis, skin disorder.**INTRODUCTION**

As per Ayurveda causes of all varieties of skin diseases are common. Intake of mutually contradictory food (virudhanna) is cause of skin disorder. Intake of this food causes vitiation of tridosha and that will be responsible for various skin disorder. Ekakushta is compared with psoriasis due to its maximum resemblance with sign and symptoms. Acharya Charaka mentions skin description under Kushtha chapter. Dry skin and raised rough, red areas on the skin covered with fine silvery scales, erythematous, well defined dry scaly papules and plaques ranges from pin head to palm sized are the symptoms seen in this disease. As per Acharya Charaka the vitiation of tridosha along with twaka, mansa, rakta and lasika have major role in pathogenesis of psoriasis. So Ayurveda Shodhan and Shaman Chikitsa is very effective in treating psoriasis. So in present case study Virechan therapy followed by Internal medicine is followed for the management of psoriasis.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 14 year female patient presented with OPD of Rani Dullaiya Smriti Ayurved college Bhopal with a chief complaint of chronic plaque over chest region, trunk region, both hands and legs and scalp with Daha, vaivarnya, kandu all over body since 5 years. Patient had disturbed sleep since 1 month. The case was diagnosed as shidmkushta on the basis of Ahara, Vihara, Nidana and Lakshana and its management is successfully done by the Ayurvedic principle Shodhan and Shamana Chikitsa.

Ashta vidha Pariksha

Sr. No	Pariksha	Pramana
1	Nadi	- 76/min
2	Mala	- Vibandha
3	Mutra	- Samyak
4	Jeeva	- Saam
5	Shabda	- Samyak
6	Sparsha	- Khar
7	Druka	- Samyak

8 Akroti - Madhyama.

Treatment Plan

Treatment plan consist of Shodhan and Shaman Chikitsa.

1. Shodhan Chikitsa– Virechan karma was carried out in shodhan chikitsa. only nitya virechan 2 tab erandbhrusth haritaki at night 10 days with Luke worm water.

2. Shamana Chikitsa– After shodhana oral medicine was started such as prosogrit 2 tab bd, panchnibhadi vati 2 tab bd, gandhak rasayan 2tab bd, mahamajisthadi kasaya 20 ml BD, bakuchi oil local application at night.

RESULTS

Redness of skin was markly reduced after treatment. Scaling was reduced significantly after treatment. Daha, vaivarnya, kandu was also reduced after treatment. The patient can sleep well after 15 days of treatment.

DISCUSSION

Shodhan and Shamana chikitsa is the key factor in Ayurved management of psoriasis. Due to virechan karma the vitiated doshas are left out of the body and samayak awastha of doshas was achieved. Shaman chikitsa also plays important role in achieving remaining vitiated doshas in samyak awastha. Local applicant coconut oil is a fantastic natural skin moisturizer and softner. It has antibacterial, antimicrobial, antifungal and anti-inflammatory properties.

CONCLUSION

By considering results of this case it can be conclude that Shodhan karma(Body purification therapy) and Shaman karma(Paliative and Conservative therapy) plays an important role in the management of Psoriasis.

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